

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF EDUCATION POLICIES AND THEIR IMPACT ON CREATIVITY: A CASE STUDY OF TURKIYE AND FRANCE

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Abstract

Education plays a pivotal role in shaping the future of a nation by influencing the mindsets of communities. Education has a direct impact on various skills, and creativity is no exception. Conversely, creativity serves as a valuable tool to enhance the educational process. Modern perspective reveals that while students with high IQ levels achieve high academic grades; those who possess outstanding creative abilities in addition to high IQ levels are one step ahead of them. Moreover, as Torrence remarked, the value of creativity to individuals is that it can be taught and developed (1972).

The connection between culture and creativity is profound and intricate. Cultural factors play a substantial role in shaping how creativity is conceptualized, defined, and recognized. Cultural diversity sparks creative synthesis and innovation, while cultural norms can both nurture and restrict creative expression. In turn, creativity is a potent force that can transform and challenge cultures, reshaping the way societies view the world.

Based on this perspective, this study delves into the intricate landscape of education policies in Türkiye and France, aiming to discern the place of creativity as a strategy in them. By scrutinizing the historical, cultural, and socio-economic contexts that underpin these policies, this research seeks to illuminate the divergent paths these two nations have taken in shaping the creative potential of their respective education systems. Drawing upon an array of qualitative and quantitative data sources, including government documents and academic literature review, this comparative analysis investigates the strategies, curricula, and pedagogical approaches employed in fostering creativity in Turkish and French schools. It explores how educational philosophies and priorities have evolved over time, and the ways in which they have contributed to or hindered the cultivation of creative thinking among students. Additionally, this study aims to shed light on the cultural nuances and societal expectations that may impact creativity within educational contexts, providing insights into the influence of the culture on policy changes.

The preliminary findings reveal that education policies play a fundamental role in shaping the creativity of students in Turkey and France. While further research and data analysis are required to draw comprehensive conclusions, it is evident that differences in educational structures, teacher training, assessment methods, cultural influences, and resource allocation have a substantial impact on fostering creativity in students.

Understanding these distinctions can provide valuable insights for policymakers, educators, and researchers in both countries, ultimately contributing to the development of more effective and creative education systems.

Keywords: Creativity, education, cross-cultural comparison, policy